

EFFECT OF INTERMINGLED WHISKER ON INTERLAMINAR STRENGTH OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In order to reinforce the interlaminar of laminated composites, a novel method was proposed. In this method, ferromagnetic whisker was added in the matrix to reinforce the interlaminar and orientation of whisker was controlled by loading magnetic moment to improve efficiency of whisker reinforcement. It was shown that, by controlling whisker orientation to the direction of the thickness, the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was improved remarkably but the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness and interlaminar shear strength were not. The improvement of the toughness reached the maximum value at the whisker volume fraction that was 10% of the continuous fiber. To improve the shear properties, it was suggested to make the whisker orient three-dimensionally random.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most serious shortcomings of the laminate composites is weakness in the interlaminar. It has not been necessarily considered seriously because most of laminate composites was applied to thin and deployable planer plate. Thus for this kind of application, interlaminar stresses are considered to be small. For the cases of thick plates or parts with complex shape that were inevitably subjected to tri-axial stresses, however, the weak interlaminar often lead to fatal fracture even in a low loading condition. To improve interlaminar strength, several measures, such as the stitching^{1,2} and the use of 3D fabrics as reinforcement³, have been proposed. These methods, however, have not been frequently used in actual applications due to low efficiency and/or low applicability.

A novel method by the use of a hybrid composite is proposed in this paper to improve the interlaminar strength of the laminate composites. The concept of the interlaminar reinforcement is shown in Fig.1 where whisker dispersed in the matrix of carbon fiber reinforced composite (CFRP), is oriented perpendicular to the plane of the interlaminar. The whisker in the composite is expected to play a role of the reinforcement to the direction of thickness. As discussed earlier^{4,5}, the orientation control of the whisker can be performed by loading magnetic moment wherein, in order to let the whisker response magnetic field, ferromagnetic coating was applied on the whisker.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

The forming process of the hybrid composite is explained in Fig.2. In the process, a bundle of carbon fibers (Toray T300 6kfila.) was firstly submerged in suspension of methanol and whisker to intermingle the whisker among the bundle of the fibers. The ultrasonic vibration applied to the suspension was to loosen the bundle of carbon fibers and to facilitate uniform mixing of the whisker and the continuous fiber. The original whisker was of SiC that is commercially available by Tateho Chemical but only the fraction with high aspect ratio was selected and used for experiments to maintain high efficiency of reinforcement. The average length and diameter of the used whisker were 23 μ m and 0.39 μ m, respectively and, as mentioned earlier,

ferromagnetic nickel alloy was coated on the whisker. Then by the conventional procedure of the filament winding process, prepreg sheet unidirectionally reinforced by the carbon fibers, matrix of which was epoxy resin, was obtained as shown in Fig.2. The prepreg sheets thus prepared were cut into the size of a mould cavity and laminated by setting the orientation uniform. Finally, magnetic moment ($1.6 \times 10^6 \text{ A/m}$) and ultrasonic vibration (7 W/cm^2) were loaded for 30min to the laminate in a circular mold cavity (diameter: 10cm) and after that the pressure (100 kgf/cm^2) was applied to the laminate. The role of the ultrasonic vibration was to loosen a tangled structure and to facilitate whisker orientation control. In the forming process the temperature of the mold was controlled by $80^\circ \text{C} \times 40 \text{ min} + 120^\circ \text{C} \times 3 \text{ h}$ and the thickness of the formed laminates were arranged to be about 3mm.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three kinds of measurements by the configurations shown in Fig.3 were carried out to evaluate (a) interlaminar shear strength (ILSS), (b) mode I (cleavage) fracture toughness (MIIFT), and (c) mode II (inplane shear) fracture toughness (MIIFT). In the figure, a_0 denotes initial crack length, which was introduced by inserting Teflon film of $30 \mu\text{m}$ on the center plane of the laminates. a_0 was set to be about 10mm. The actual measurement was started after the crack extended over 15mm. For MIIFT specimen to let the initial crack propagate to the length of about 15mm, the aluminum tabs same as for MIIFT were adhered and cleavage load was applied before the MIIFT test. Instron Universal Materials Testing Machine was used for the experiments under the crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min . MIIFT specimen was loaded through aluminum tabs and iteration of loading/unloading, in each step approximately 5mm length of crack was newly growing, were performed on each specimen. The crack opening displacement (COD) was regarded as the same value as the displacement of the machine crosshead due to high rigidity of test fixture. The crack length, a , was measured with a vernier microscope and the compliance, C , was obtained from the load vs. COD curves. A third degree polynomial was fitted to the C vs. a curve by the method of the least squares. Then by the substitution dC/da into eq.(1)⁶, we obtained G_I .

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2w} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (1)$$

where G_I :MIIFT, P : the load at the point of crack-arrest and w : the width of the specimen.

MIIFT and ILSS specimens were subjected to 3-point flexural loading. In Mode II testing, linear elastic response was observed up to quasi-unstable crack growth. Then the crack was used to deviate toward the loading point and catastrophic fracture was occurred. This behavior was especially frequently observed in the hybrid composite. The maximum load was therefore used for the value in eq.(2)⁷

$$G_{II} = \frac{P^2 a^2}{16w^2 E_b h^3} \quad (2)$$

where G_{II} :MIIFT, E_b :flexural modulus and h :half-thickness.

The shear strength was evaluated by the widely used short beam method and ILSS was obtained by eq.(3)⁸

$$\tau = \frac{3P}{4wH} \quad (3)$$

where P :maximum load and H :thickness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Let us confirm at first that the whisker in the laminates was oriented to the direction of through the thickness as the concept of Fig.1. Fig. 4 is typical SEM photograph of MIIFT fracture surface. It is obvious from the figure that many of the whisker, thin and short fiber, orients to the vertical direction (thickness direction

of the sample) and effectively resists against increase of the COD as verified by the ruin of the pulling out of the whisker. Thus G_I is expected to increase by the addition of the whisker. Fig.5. shows results of the G_I measurements where the plotted data was the average values of three test pieces. In the figure, the open circle stands for the composites reinforced only by the carbon fiber and the closed circle for the hybrid composite and the whisker content of the closed circles No.2, 4, and 6 are 2.0, 1.0, and 1.4 volume percent, respectively. Thus the discrepancy between the open and closed circles denotes the effect of the orientation-controlled whisker and toughness increase by the whisker can be estimated as 2.5 times of the original composite.

On the other hand, G_{II} was not sensitive to the addition of the orientation-controlled whisker as shown in Fig.6. It is apparent that fiber orientation of 45° is the most effective for reinforcement against shear loading. Therefore, if we get the randomly orientating whisker as shown Fig.1(a), G_{II} possibly increases by the whisker addition. This experiment is now under consideration.

Finally, results of the ILSS tests are shown in Table 1. The results appears to show degradation of ILSS. However, fracture mode of the whisker added composite was clearly by bending mode, namely initial fracure ocured by tension mode at the just underside of the loading point due to damage of carbon fibers during prepreg making process. Thus, this results don't necessarily mean that the present method is not effective to raise ILSS.

Table 1 Experimental results of ILLS

Specimen	V_f [%]	V_{sicw} [%]	τ [MPa]
CFRP	52	—	82.1
HYBRID COMPOSITE	44	0.7	68.5
	48	1.0	52.2

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Fig.1 Concept of the Hybrid composite

Fig.2 Forming Process of the Hybrid composite

Fig.3 Shapes and dimensions of Test specimens
 (a) Interlaminar Shear Strength
 (b) Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness
 (c) Mode II Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Fig.4 Typical SEM photograph of Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Surface

Fig.5 Effect of Intermingled whisker on Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Fig.6 Effect of Intermingled whisker on Mode II Interlaminar Fracture Toughness